

Coping with cancer: A discourse and thematic analysis of adolescents' metaphor preferences

Rosita MAGLIE, University of Bari, Italy¹

Francesca FILOGRASSO, University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy

Germana CASTORO, Hospital of Bari Policlinico Giovanni XXIII, Italy

The literature on the topic of cancer metaphors in health communication is substantial. However, there is surprisingly little research on how metaphors are used by and influence young patients. This study examines how adolescent cancer patients use metaphors to describe cancer, and discusses this usage as it relates to coping strategies compared to healthy adolescents. Data was based on eight recorded semi-structured interviews about cancer metaphors from the Metaphor Menu for People with Cancer, which were analyzed using thematic and discourse analysis. Findings show that adolescent patients and nonpatients most frequently chose the New Value metaphor and used problem-focused coping strategies. The results improve our understanding of how adolescents perceive and experience cancer, and provide a revealing perspective on their emotional wellbeing and social interactions.

Keywords: Adolescents; Cancer Metaphor; Coping Strategies; Discourse Analysis; Thematic Analysis

1. Introduction

Cancer is a complex and emotionally fraught disease that is often described using metaphors. Cancer description using metaphors has often been studied from the perspectives of adults and healthcare providers with little attention given to adolescents' viewpoints on the matter (Harrington, 2012; Lanceley & Clark, 2013; Woodgate & Busolo, 2017). Family members, educators, healthcare providers and public discourse shape the way young people think and talk about, and experience cancer. These cancer messages to adolescents can expand or limit their perceptions of the world and their agency in dealing with cancer.

The study we conducted was one of the first of its kind in Italy to examine the use of cancer metaphors among adolescents, contributing foundational

¹ Corresponding Author: rosita.maglie@uniba.it

knowledge to understanding adolescents' attitude toward cancer. Understanding how young people perceive, emotionally engage with, and discursively construct cancer via metaphors will shed light on their perceptions and preventive behaviors related to cancer as well as on how they will eventually support friends and relatives dealing with cancer.

The paper begins with a review of the literature on the use of metaphors in health communication about cancer. It then introduces our ongoing multidisciplinary project called 'A Metaphor for Change' before presenting the pilot study that was conducted using the interview technique and a collection of different metaphors inserted into an online menu by Semino and other colleagues at Lancaster University (i.e., Metaphor Menu for People with Cancer, launched online in November 2019).¹ It then discusses the findings that emerged from the thematic and discourse analysis of the respondents' answers in relation to the metaphors selected from the menu, new and more personal metaphors, as well as their coping strategies. The study ends with some concluding remarks and suggestions for further studies and future health communication practices.

2. Background

Metaphors allow individuals to personalize their experiences and perceptions of cancer. The literature consulted shows that health professionals use metaphors to promote understanding and empathy (Casarett et al., 2010; Harrington, 2012), but their careless use by clinicians can risk misinterpretation and confusion among patients and caregivers. The promotion of a 'fighting' attitude by clinicians, for example, may be interpreted by patients as the need to suppress emotional expression (Byrne et al., 2002). Thus, the deployment of metaphors in healthcare necessitates more research, training, and expertise to ensure they are used skillfully and effectively. Moreover, it has been found that the use of interdisciplinary teams in the evaluation of metaphorical language in healthcare can provide perspectives and insights into discourse strategies that ensure that metaphors truly "personalize challenging discussions, improve patient comprehension, and help patients and their families to plan ahead" (Hui et al., 2018, p. 730).

For cancer patients, the use of metaphors both reflects and affects thinking. Metaphors provide them with a way to give voice to their experiences in a more relatable way, to approach their feelings indirectly, to manage uncertainty, and to find meaning in their illness (Gibbs & Franks, 2002). The metaphors they use influence their emotional coping, the transformative impact of cancer on their identity, and their communication with healthcare providers. The study by Jerome and Liaw (2020) confirms that patients use different types of metaphors to discuss their experiences with the disease, providing insights

into their risk perceptions and efficacy beliefs. Analyzing the variety of source domains in patient stories can help healthcare professionals, caregivers, and researchers better comprehend the psychological and emotional response of patients to the disease and eventually enhance communication and support in cancer care. For instance, War metaphors² may not resonate with everyone (Guité-Verret & Vachon, 2021). They can have both positive (i.e., they help patients frame cancer positively, fostering hope and resilience) and negative (i.e., they cause patients to blame themselves when treatment does not work) effects on emotional wellbeing, thus requiring consideration within each patient's unique context (Hurley, 2014).

In the literature consulted, healthy people were also studied, but their use of metaphors was not analyzed. Rather, Fernandez et al. (2022) focus on the effects of metaphors on healthy people's behavior related to cancer risk reduction. Metaphors not only help them make sense of cancer but also shape their emotional response and relationships with cancer patients, as well as their coping styles, health beliefs, and engagement in preventive behaviors. For instance, bellicose metaphors for cancer can influence the health beliefs of nonpatients in ways that may make them less willing to enact healthy behavior (e.g., perceiving treatment as more difficult may lead to demotivation and potential resistance to health beliefs) (Hauser & Schwarz, 2015, 2020). Public health messaging should aim to avoid demotivating individuals, promoting reactance against messages, and reducing the likelihood of engagement in preventive behaviors.

Little is known—as mentioned earlier—about how adolescent cancer patients perceive or understand cancer, and it is not yet clear how metaphors influence their feelings. The few studies found are aimed at understanding how cancer was talked about, represented, and perceived by adolescent nonpatients, confirming the impact of metaphors on their emotions (Mooney-Somers et al., 2016; Woodgate & Busolo, 2017). Military metaphors, the most frequently used by adolescents, may have detrimental effects on cancer prevention efforts and on the experiences of individuals with cancer. Further research is needed to explore alternative constructions of young people who have had cancer as they may help peers imagine ways to express themselves beyond the victim narrative.

Cancer experiences are not perceived by people in the same way. Rather, personal, diverse, and often contradictory metaphors are used to transform the disease into a meaningful experience for healthcare professionals, patients, and healthy young people. Patients are the most productive, because for them no single metaphor alone can capture the complexity of their thinking about cancer. Semino et al. (2017, 2018) provide a comprehensive examination of the metaphors used by patients, family caregivers, and healthcare professionals

when talking about cancer and end-of-life experiences. They conclude that while violent metaphors, such as *dying after a battle with cancer*, are generally rejected due to their potentially disempowering connotations, the appropriateness of a metaphor depends on its context, function and individual perception, and varies according to the three actors in the healthcare system (i.e., healthcare professionals, family caregivers, and patients). For example, patients use violent metaphors to convey determination (e.g., express desire and attempt to get better/recover, express a fighting spirit and positive attitude) but also fear (e.g., express worry and negative perception of lack of recovery if treatment fails). Caregivers use violence metaphors to express difficulties and the emotional toll related to their relationships with patients (i.e., a sense of oppression) and to the grief of loss (i.e., feelings of devastation). Doctors use Fight and Battle metaphors, for instance, to express the feeling associated with the perceived sense of responsibility for the patient (i.e., they are described as being in a leadership position in a war) and to describe the symptoms and side effects of cancer treatment (Potts & Semino, 2017).

3. Method

The findings presented in this paper were obtained from the pilot study of the project 'A Metaphor for Change' that uses a systematic protocol to examine a sample of healthy adolescents (control group) and adolescent patients from the Pediatric Onomatology Unit of the Bari University Hospital (experimental group), in collaboration with the Psychology Department of the Children's Hospital 'Giovanni XXIII' of Bari. This project has three objectives: to develop a visual language capable of articulating the subjective illness experiences of adolescent patients, to promote individual and social adaptation to cancer, and to strengthen the relationship between patients and healthcare professionals.

A qualitative approach was used, including (1) discourse analysis³ and (2) thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews with the adolescents to identify overarching themes. The combination of these two types of analysis has been used before (e.g., Botelle & Willott, 2020; Braun & Clarke, 2006; Taylor & Ussher, 2001) and is ideally suited to the study of personal experience and meaning. It involves a rigorous exploration of linguistic patterns, metaphorical constructions and emotional expressions, enabling researchers to systematically identify thematic patterns in participants' spoken narratives. Data analysis of the results relied on the transcriptions of semi-structured interviews using the Italian translation (by the first author of this study) of the Metaphor Menu. The audio recordings were carefully transcribed and repeatedly read to ensure accuracy and understanding of the key emotional and cognitive aspects expressed by the participants. The data were coded by the authors based on the basic content and then categorized accordingly. Themes were developed to capture the most important aspects of participants'

responses. The overarching themes emerged from a combination of linguistic metaphor analysis of the metaphor types [M1-17] selected by the participants from the Metaphor Menu, together with the reasons they gave for their metaphor choices and the new and more personal metaphors they were asked to provide, as well as the authors' consensus on the thematic relevance to the study objectives. This thematic framework, enriched by participants' personal coping strategies and health beliefs, provided clinical insights into their cancer experiences. Applying discourse analysis, the themes were then analyzed at a deeper level to determine what, if anything, they reveal about broader societal discourses related to cancer.

3.1. Participants

The project participants, aged between 14 and 18, were assessed as having average cognitive functioning using the Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test (KBIT-2). The control group consists of nonpatients and the experimental group of patients with cancer recruited in different treatment phases such as therapy, maintenance therapy, and stop therapy.

3.2. Materials

Participants completed emotional and cognitive questionnaires. The Kaufman Brief Intelligence Test (KBIT-2), a brief measure of verbal and nonverbal intelligence for individuals aged 4 to 90 years (Kaufman, 1990), was selected to assess participants' cognitive functioning, with internal consistency reliability above 0.90 for the age range included in the current study. The Interview Attachment Latency (IAL), a revised version of the Adult Attachment Interview (AAI) tailored for late childhood and early adolescence (Ammaniti et al., 1990), was used to assess participants' attachment styles. The coding system, developed by Main and Goldwyn (1985-1994) and adapted for use in Italy by Ammaniti et al. (1990), classifies adolescents into four categories regarding their overall state of mind with respect to attachment: (a) secure, (b) dismissing of attachment relationships, (c) preoccupied with attachment relationships, and (d) unresolved with respect to past loss or trauma. The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) and The General Anxiety Disorder-7 (GAD-7) were selected to explore the emotional states reported by the adolescents. The PHQ-9 (Kroenke et al., 2001; Spitzer et al., 1999) is a self-administered diagnostic tool for assessing depression severity, exhibiting 88% sensitivity and specificity for major depression. The GAD-7 is a self-administered questionnaire designed to screen for and measure the severity of generalized anxiety disorder (GAD) based on DSM-IV diagnostic criteria (Spitzer et al., 2006); a threshold score of 10 demonstrates 89% sensitivity and 82% specificity for GAD. The Illness Perceptions Questionnaire-Revised (IPQ-R), administered only to the experimental group, is an 84-item self-completed

instrument developed to quantitatively measure components of illness representations (Giardini et al., 2007; Weinman et al., 1996), as described by Leventhal's Common-Sense Model (CSM) of self-regulation (Leventhal, 1982; Leventhal & Colman, 1997). The semi-structured interviews were based on the Italian translation of the Metaphor Menu for People with Cancer (Demjén & Semino, 2020), which was selected to investigate the impact of metaphors on patients' emotional wellbeing and the formulation of new, more personal cancer conceptualizations. The Menu comprises seventeen metaphors (M) which belong to the following categories: Fairground ride [M1],⁴ Journey [M2-M5], Stone in a shoe [M6], Fight [M7-M8], Not a Fight [M9-M11], Music [M12], Invasion [M13-M14], New Value [M15], and Nature [M16-M17]. A pre-determined set of open questions (e.g., Do you know the word 'cancer'? Could you choose four metaphors from the Metaphor Menu? Which metaphor would you choose to describe this disease?) explored the disease representations and imagery preferred by the adolescents. Participants were also asked to give reasons for their metaphor choice. The questions used with the experimental group also explored perceptions of the relationship between healthcare professionals and patients, as well as relationships between patients and their parents and friends. For this article all responses were translated from Italian into English [by the first author of this study], then the individual linguistic expressions and verbatim extracts from our data reported here were written in italics and the salient words highlighted in bold type.

3.3. Procedure

Data collection took place in different settings and locations (e.g., at home or in the hospital). The procedure included two clinical interviews conducted with the participants by a trained psychologist (the second author of this paper). The first interview aimed to collect personal data and obtain information about individual and social functioning. For the experimental group, the first interview also focused on illness behavior and emotional stress reactions. During this phase, the adolescents completed the PHQ-9, the GAD-7, and the KBIT-2 to assess cognitive performance. In the second part of the interview, which was audio-recorded, the psychologist used the Metaphor Menu to ask semi-structured questions created ad hoc to explore participants' cancer representations and metaphors/images. During the second clinical interview, participants completed the AICA to assess attachment security. In addition, the experimental group completed the IPQR to examine perceptions/representations of the disease condition.

3.4. Ethics

The project was approved by the Ethics Committee of the IRCCS Istituto Tumori 'Giovanni Paolo II' on May 9, 2024, and received permission from the

Pediatric Onomatology Unit of the Bari University Hospital. Prior to data collection, parents/guardians received an information letter, and participants received a separate letter. Participation required signed consent from both adolescents and their parents/guardians.

4. Results

A total of eight participants completed the interviews based on the Italian translation of the Lancaster Metaphor Menu. The experimental group consisted of four participants, who were predominantly male (3/1; 75%) and had an average age of 17.2 years ($SD = 1.2$; range 15-19). The control group also comprised four participants who were predominantly female (3/1; 75%) and had an average age of 16.6 years ($SD = 1.4$; range 14-18). The socio-demographic data and family backgrounds revealed that two adolescents in the control group (Nonpatients #2 and #4) had a relative diagnosed with cancer. The thematic analysis of the eight interview transcripts revealed three overarching themes: coping strategies, metaphors, and new metaphors.

4.1. Coping strategies

The coping strategies 'used' by the participants in the experimental and control groups were identified using the model designed by Carver et al. (1989) and Carver (1997), which describes 14 primary coping strategies: four problem-focused strategies, six emotion-focused strategies, and four avoidance strategies. The analysis provided a detailed comparison of the 83 references to coping strategies identified in the transcripts. It was found that these references were distributed in different proportions between the experimental group (62.6%) and the control group (37.3%). In terms of the problem-focused strategies, the experimental group showed a higher tendency for active coping (6% vs. 4.8%), use of informational support (7.2% vs. 3.6%), and positive reframing (10.8% vs. 4.8%). Planning was also slightly more common in the experimental group (2.4% compared to 1.2%). Conversely, the control group used these strategies less frequently overall. As regards the emotion-focused coping, the experimental group reported more frequent use of emotional support (13.2% vs. 3.6%) and venting (4.8% vs. 1.2%), while humor was more common in the control group (3.6% vs. 1.2%). Acceptance was significantly higher in the control group (9.6% vs. 1.2%) and both groups had similarly low scores for religious coping (1.2%). In terms of avoidance strategies, the experimental group had a higher frequency of denial (7.2% vs. 2.4%) and behavioral disengagement (3.6% vs. 0%). Self-distraction was more common in the experimental group (2.4% vs. 1.2%), while substance use, and self-blame were not reported in either group. Overall, the experimental group appeared to use more varied coping strategies compared to the control group.

4.2. Metaphors from the metaphor menu

Selecting metaphors from the Metaphor Menu that best represented the adolescents' conception of cancer provided them with a way of dealing with the emotional, physical, and existential challenges associated with living with cancer. In the experimental group, Journey [M5] and Fight [M8] were chosen three times, followed by Not a Fight [M11], and New Value [M15] twice. Fairground ride [M1], Journey [M3], Stone in a Shoe [M6], Fight [M7], Not a Fight [M10], and Nature [M16] were the least frequently chosen metaphors. In the control group, New Value [M15] was the most chosen metaphor, as it was chosen three times, followed by Fairground Ride [M1], Not a Fight [M9], and Invasion [M13, M14]. Journey [M3], Fight [M7], Stone in a Shoe [M6], Not a Fight [M11], and Nature [M16] were only chosen once. When we added up all the metaphors chosen by the two groups, we got that New Value [M15] (15.6%) is the most chosen metaphor, followed by Fairground Ride [M1] (9.3%), Journey [M5] (9.3%), Fight [M8] (9.3%), and Not a Fight [M11] (9.3%). Journey [M3], Stone in a Shoe [M6], Fight [M7], Not a Fight [M9], Invasion [M13, M14], and Nature [M16] came after with the same percentage of 6.25%. Not a Fight [M10] was the least chosen metaphor (3.1%). When we wanted to know who chose what, we realized that the metaphor choice can either be reserved for only one group or that no clear distinction can be made between the two groups. An example of the first case is Journey [M5], which was chosen only by the experimental group, as well as Invasion [M13, M14] and Not a Fight [M9], which were chosen only by the control group. The following examples, which are the most numerous, illustrate the second case in which the choice of metaphor was not group-dependent, as both patients and nonpatients showed to generally choose the same metaphors. For example, Patients #1, #2, and #4 had the Fight [M5] and Patients #1, #2, and #3 the Journey [M5] metaphors in common, confirming that these two metaphors are the most salient types used by cancer patients (cf. Demmen et. al, 2015; Semino et al. 2017). However, the same metaphor categories, but different types (i.e., Fight [M7] and Journey [M3]), were also chosen by Nonpatients #2 and #3, respectively. Patient #1 chose the same Fairground Ride metaphor as Nonpatients #2 and #3. Patients #3 and #4 chose the metaphors Not a Fight [M10 and M11], which were also preferred by Nonpatients #1 for the type [M11], and #2 and #3 for the same category but other types [M7 and M9]. Patient #2 chose the metaphor Nature, which was also favored by Nonpatient #4.

4.3. New metaphors

The variety of source domains used in the new metaphors, which patients and nonpatients were asked to formulate, shows how differently the experience of cancer can be perceived and articulated. Patient #2 compares cancer to a level in a video game. Patients #3 and #4 draw from the same source domain to

frame their metaphors, i.e., the world of Nature (atmospheric phenomena and insects). The former talks of a storm in summer, the latter refers to the process of metamorphosis: the caterpillar that changes into a butterfly. Nonpatient #1 depicts cancer as two individuals, one stronger than the other, holding a thread representing luck; in the end, the weaker surrenders to the stronger. Nonpatient #2 discursively structures the disease as a make-up product, i.e., the waterproof mascara. Nonpatients #3 and #4 share the same source domain and conceptualize cancer as a Journey.

5. Discussion

5.1 Coping strategies

The results of this pilot study are consistent with the existing literature on coping strategies in adolescents diagnosed with cancer (Belpame et al., 2021), as they emphasize the complexity and variability of young patients' psychological responses to the disease and provide a meaningful comparison with healthy adolescents. Studies have shown that adolescents with cancer often resort to a combination of problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies to deal with both the physical and emotional challenges of their diagnosis (Compas et al., 2012; Phipps et al., 2017). For example, the experimental group in this study used positive reframing and informational support more frequently than the control group, reflecting a proactive approach to coping by seeking understanding and finding positive perspectives. As Patient #4 expressed, "*In the end I am very **grateful** for the illness because it made me discover parts of myself that I didn't know before . . . it made me appreciate every situation, every moment of life more,*" describing how cancer changed his outlook on life. Similarly, Patient #1 highlighted the role of healthcare providers in reducing his anxiety: "*I have managed to become more aware of what the illness was . . . **thanks to** the doctors who calmed me down.*" These strategies are consistent with previous research showing that adolescents with chronic illnesses such as cancer often use active coping strategies and seek information to gain a sense of control over their course of treatment (Clarke-Steffen, 1997; Zebrack et al., 2014). However, healthy adolescents may not face the same intensity of stress, which may explain why they are less likely to use such strategies.

In terms of emotion-focused coping, the experimental group reported more frequent use of emotional support and venting, which is consistent with the literature, and which emphasizes the essential role of social support systems in coping with the emotional burden of illness (Hildenbrand et al., 2011; Rosenberg et al., 2013). Patient #2 explained the sense of connection he felt in the hospital "*Nevertheless I felt a great **closeness** both to my parents and here in the hospital . . . in hospital you really don't have the feeling of being outside the*

world . . . *you feel like everyone else.*" Conversely, humor was more common in the control group, a strategy often associated with coping with everyday stress. Research suggests that humor is a more common response in situations with less intense stressors, suggesting that healthy adolescents resort to lighter emotional responses to cope with daily challenges (Folkman & Moskowitz, 2000).

An important finding that further refines the understanding of coping in the control group is the fact that adolescents who had witnessed the illness of a close family member, such as a sibling or parent, tended to use coping strategies that were similar to those of the experimental group. The literature supports the idea that adolescents affected by a serious illness of a family member, especially life-threatening illnesses, develop problem- and emotion-focused strategies similar to those of the patients themselves (Melhem et al., 2007; Thastum et al., 2008). In addition, these adolescents find themselves in a more advanced stage of the acceptance process compared to cancer patients, likely because time had passed since their family member's illness, allowing for better emotional processing and adjustment (Kazak et al., 2001). As Nonpatient #2 shared, *"I think the first step to stop feeling so bad is to first **accept that it exists** . . . And then . . . just live as if it's the only time you have to live."* Nonpatient #4 also reflected on his father's illness and described his positive attitude during the illness: *"During the illness we understood how it ended, but he always had a smile in his eyes . . . everyone who remembers him remembers him as the person who always had a smile."*

The study also highlights the increased use of avoidance strategies in the experimental group, particularly denial (7.2% vs. 2.4%) and behavioral disengagement (3.6% vs. 0%). When confronted with an overwhelming stressor such as cancer, adolescents often used these strategies as psychological protection. They provide short-term relief by helping individuals distance themselves from difficult realities (Aldridge & Roesch, 2007; Carver et al., 1989). Patient #3 remarked how she struggled with shock and disbelief: *"I couldn't believe it . . . I wondered why this was happening to me . . . it seemed more like a **joke** than anything else."* However, these strategies can lead to maladaptation if used extensively, as they prevent individuals from effectively processing their emotional experiences in the long term. In contrast, the healthy adolescents in the control group resorted to avoidance strategies less frequently, probably because they were not confronted with significant stressors and therefore did not require such intensive psychological protective measures.

The differences observed between the two groups illustrate the psychological challenges faced by adolescents with a cancer diagnosis. The experimental group used a wider range of coping strategies, from denial of the diagnosis to more functional approaches, depending on the stage of their illness. In

contrast, the control group, especially those who had already experienced illness in their family, benefited from greater temporal and emotional distance from the acute phase, enabling them to use more adaptive strategies such as acceptance (Kazak et al., 2001; Zebrack & Chesler, 2001).

5.2. Metaphors from the menu and new metaphors

The preliminary results of this pilot study contribute to our understanding of how cancer metaphors function in health communication and social psychological research, shedding light on the specific individual and situational factors associated with metaphor preferences. The selection of four favorite metaphors from the menu offered a way for both patients and nonpatients to navigate the emotional, physical, and existential challenges of living with cancer. For brevity, only the reasons for the most salient and frequent metaphor types are reported here, i.e., The New Value and Fight. The New Value is from the Lancaster Metaphor Menu and was the most frequently chosen by both patients (#2 and #4) and nonpatients (#1, #3, and #4). Through it Patient #2 refers to cancer and to previous “*things*” that were thought “*to be normal*” and that they turned out to be impossible after the therapy, since “*those who are in this situation could not experience ordinary things because they had to go through the therapy.*” Patient #4 expresses a change of perspective and a renewed outlook on life amidst the struggles, such as “*school*” and “*the contact with classmates.*” Looking at the literature on the cancer metaphor, the New Value can be equated with two other source domains, i.e., the Unveiling or the Lesson, used to convey the experience of this disease (Feralda et al., 2022; Guité-Verret & Vachon, 2021). All adolescents seem here to attempt to lift the veil on the complicated nature of living with cancer in order to give new value to life. When explaining their motivation for choosing the New Value metaphor, they emphasized the challenges that the disease brings and the potential for learning and growth that can result from the experience of dealing with the illness, as well as acceptance and a renewed perspective on life. Nonpatient #1 stated that people with cancer “*value everything more*” than healthy people and Nonpatient #3 referred specifically to healthy young people who “*tend not to appreciate what life gives them every day.*” For Nonpatient #4 the metaphor makes him recall the last days of his dad and “*his love for the things you do every day.*”

The Fight metaphor also comes from the menu and was the second most frequently chosen, together with other metaphor categories (i.e., Fairground Ride, Journey, and Not a Fight). The decision to discuss only the Fight metaphor here is confirmed by the literature on violent metaphors in relation to cancer, which underlines how much they persist in public discourse, in slogans of cancer research organizations and in scientific reporting on cancer, thus influencing the mindset of adolescents (Fernandez et al., 2022). However,

violent metaphors are not unambiguous, i.e., they can either positively or negatively affect how patients and nonpatients approach the disease (Demmen et al. 2015; Semino et al., 2017). Patient #1 chooses the Fight metaphor to express his desire and aspiration to get well/recover soon (*“it [= the difficult and unpleasant situation] would be temporary . . . will come to an end sooner or later”*), and to present himself as active and determined (*“I had the **grit** to face this challenge”*). Both patients #1 and #2 use it with a positive attitude (*“If you are **positive**, you can’t get down emotionally”*—Patient #1; *“You have to face it with a **smile**”*—Patient #2). But, although patient #2, like Nonpatient #2, mentions the complexity of the cancer experience (*“cancer demands a lot from you . . . is something that should not be underestimated”*—Patient #2); he does not do so with the same negative connotation as Nonpatient #2, confirming that the use of metaphors should be evaluated not only on the basis of their nature (‘Fight’ or ‘Not a Fight’), but also on the basis of their function and individual perception. For Nonpatient #2 cancer *“is like a fight because they [patients] don’t know what is in front of them, there is someone **bigger**.”* While the Fight metaphor evokes vigilance and action in patients, it does not motivate action, as in Nonpatient #2, when imagining an individual fighting cancer. Within the latter unique context, the Fight metaphor has a disempowering effect on her emotional wellbeing, which may negatively impact her future health beliefs (Hauser & Schwarz, 2015, 2020).

The new metaphors that the participants were asked to formulate show how differently their way of thinking shapes their experience of cancer. However, they can be equated with those most used by people, mainly adolescents, when formulating their understanding and emotional responses to it (Woodgate & Busolo, 2017; Mooney-Somers et al., 2016). Patient #1 does not provide a new metaphor for cancer but sends a message of resilience and hope by using the figurative phrase *“grit your teeth”* to convey his determination to keep going. Patient #2 compares cancer to a level in a video game *“that you can’t get through . . . You try and try again, eventually with the right equipment you manage to complete it and get on with the story.”* The video game metaphor can be assimilated to the Fight category, as it reflects the challenging and combative nature of the disease (Demmen et al., 2015). It sheds light on the resilience and personal growth that can result from the cancer experience (Bodd et al., 2022). The metaphor helps him deal with the complex and uncertain aspects of cancer and therapy, and to make the difficult treatment decisions to get on with the story. Patients #3 and #4 refer to natural phenomena. The former talks of *“a storm in summer that prevents you from going outside, but when it stops you can go on doing whatever you want.”* The latter refers to the process of metamorphosis: *“the caterpillar that changes into a butterfly.”* The Living thing metaphor (i.e., the caterpillar turning into a butterfly—Patient #3) emphasizes the dynamic aspects of the disease. This

approach communicates an intuitive sense of cancer as a living entity with characteristics akin to animals (Harrington, 2012). The summer rain that eventually stops can be assimilated to the Season metaphor which helps patients to cope with the unpredictability of cancer (i.e., the storm), while reflecting the changing phases of the disease (i.e., the season) (Jerome & Liaw, 2020).

Nonpatient #1 depicts cancer as a tense relationship in which one part of a person's soul is stronger than another part, and these two parts are pulling against each other (again the theme of a Fight) by a thread, which represents luck. The patient and the illness are seen as enemies, suggesting that failure to recover is a personal defeat. Moreover, the concept of fighting cancer can overshadow the passive aspect of treatment, and the uncertainties involved, potentially creating unrealistic expectations (Hurley, 2014). However, equating the self with survival through the Fight metaphor does not have the effect described in the literature of patients being seen as those who blame themselves, but on the contrary, they are perceived by Nonpatient #1 as "*those who nevertheless decide to **fight** . . . hoping to **win** either way to the last, with the knowledge that they have at least tried to **fight** the illness.*" We also observed a lexical priming effect in Nonpatient #1. She tended to use language that matched the metaphor she was confronted with (*fight, win*). Research argues that in this case, fight metaphors for cancer may negatively influence non-patients' health beliefs such that they are less willing to engage in health-promoting behaviors (Hauser & Schwarz, 2015, 2020). Nonpatient #2 uses the original metaphor of "***waterproof** mascara that never comes off.*" It could refer both to the pain that is felt but not visible to the naked eye (again the Fight metaphor, but this time private and secret, not expressed or shown to other people) as the waterproof mascara does not allow water (tears) to pass through and destroy the make-up, and to the permanence of cancer. Nonpatients #3 and #4 share the same mindset in metaphor choice as both emphasize the dynamic and destructive aspects of the disease (Feralda et al., 2022; Hendricks et al., 2018). Nonpatient #3 talks of "*a tortuous path to cross, a line splitting into other lines . . . an ugly line, a bit all curled up, . . . not straight.*" Nonpatient #4 presents cancer "*a vortex dragging everyone down.*" Their metaphors can be thematized as Journey metaphors (Demmen et al., 2015; Semino et al. 2017), but only when used with their negative implications, as these metaphors only describe the significant difficulties faced by patients and their family members. Nonpatient #4 presents cancer, for instance, as a path to inevitable decline. Both the Journey and the Waterproof mascara represent the struggle of living with cancer and the eventual realization of the limitation of treatments and mortality associated with the disease. These nonpatients view the experience as a complex and violent journey through various medical procedures, and the disease as incurable (Guité-Verret & Vachon, 2021). The

potentially negative impact of their metaphors could affect the understanding of cancer prevention as something beyond one's control and the intention to engage in preventive behavior, such as neglecting cancer screenings, for example (Hauser & Schwarz, 2020).

All in all, the use of metaphors helped the adolescents who participated in this pilot study to make sense of cancer, enabled patients to reframe their lives to resist disruption and hope for a better future. But, the metaphors also underscore the fear, sadness and confusion associated with the disease, particularly among participants in the control group, highlighting the need for more cancer information campaigns, education and psychosocial support.

6. Conclusion

The preliminary findings of our pilot study make it extremely difficult to draw a comprehensive conclusion. However, the results make concrete contributions to the current literature. For example, the Fight metaphor helps patients to express their self-motivation and agency in terms of fighting spirit, whereas nonpatients found it less empowering. This finding confirms the literature in the field (Byrne et al., 2002). Another contribution lies in the health beliefs between patients and nonpatients. The former believe that the disease is temporary and therefore trust in the effectiveness of treatment, while the latter are convinced that cancer is life-threatening and permanent and therefore feel a sense of helplessness. These misconceptions and negative emotional reactions are described in the literature among healthy young people (Mooney-Somers et al., 2016; Woodgate & Busolo, 2017) and should be more actively discussed by educators, healthcare providers, and the public. In developing awareness communication strategies aimed at offering accurate and complete information, those metaphors that may undermine adolescents' coping mechanisms and prevention efforts should be identified and possibly avoided. While the significance of our results might be limited in range, as far as we know, ours is one of few studies that considers metaphors from the perspective of adolescent patients and nonpatients, and that highlights overlaps between linguistic metaphor analysis and psychological theories of emotion disclosure and coping. In the area of psychology, the active engagement with the adolescents' metaphors enabled the psychologist conducting the interviews not only to explore the participants' emotions and fears in depth, but also to understand and reflect on their coping processes. The experimental group showed a proactive and resilient approach to dealing with cancer, while the control group tended to use different coping strategies, which were probably influenced by the nature and intensity of the challenges they faced. In the field of linguistics, the results have helped to identify the metaphorical expressions that will be further investigated when the corpus is enlarged according to the procedure proposed by the Pragglejaz Group (2007)

and then checked for their definite metaphoricity in the corpus and in the concordance lines, using the corpus analysis software Wmatrix (Rayson, 2008). Future work based on the methods outlined here will expand our knowledge of cancer messages to adolescents that truly support young patients after cancer treatment and promote their reintegration into their social environment, support healthy coping mechanisms and prevention efforts in adolescent nonpatients, and provide alternative perspectives on people with cancer so that adolescents can envision how to relate to them beyond the loser narrative. Ultimately, we hope that this study will have an impact on doctor-patient interactions because, as the literature shows (Black, 2020; Hui et al., 2018), the use or careful selection of common and effective metaphors promotes empathy, understanding and personalized care for people with cancer, as well as patients' corrective emotional experiences and rapid changes in their perceptions of their own suffering, sense of agency, and mastery of their feelings.

Notes

1. <http://wp.lancs.ac.uk/melc/the-metaphor-menu>
2. In this paper, the groups of metaphorical expressions from a particular semantic area or category are indicated by a capital letter at the beginning, e.g., War metaphor.
3. Discourse analysis was intended here as a method that examines how individuals construct their internal understanding of phenomena through discourse (Burman, 1993).
4. In this paper, a particular metaphor type is abbreviated as M, followed by the corresponding number in the Metaphor Menu, and both type and number are placed in a square, e.g., [M 1]. If there is more than one type of metaphor category in the Metaphor Menu, the letter M and the corresponding number of metaphor types follow, with the first number indicating the first metaphor type and the last number the last type of the same metaphor category, e.g., [M2-M5].

Authors' Statement

Although this research was conceived and conducted jointly by all three authors, Rosita Maglie contributed to sections 1, 2, 4.2, 4.3, 5.2 and 6 and Francesca Filograsso worked on sections 2, 3, 3.1-3.4, 4, 4.1 and 5.1 of the article.

The Authors

Rosita Maglie (Email: rosita.maglie@uniba.it) is Associate Professor in English Language and Translation at the University of Bari. Her research focuses on Corpus-Assisted Discourse Studies, Languages for Specific Purposes, and Computer-Mediated Communication. Her publications include the chapters “The Web-Mediated Construction of Interdiscursive Truth(s) about the MMR Vaccine: A Defamation Case” (with A. F. Plastina, 2021, Routledge) and “Debunking Covid-19 Conspiracy Theories in The Digital Age: A Discourse Analysis on Spotify” (2022, CSP); and the articles “Covid-19: Exploring Linguistic Indicators of Conspiratorial Thinking in the Media: A case study of Coronacast” (with M. Groicher, 2023, *Lingue e Linguaggi*, 58), and “Developing digital health literacy amidst the Covid-19 infodemic” (with M. Groicher, 2024, *TTMC*, 10(1)).

Francesca Filograsso (Email: francesca.filograsso@uniba.it) is a Clinical Psychologist, PhD Student in Gender Studies at the University of Bari Aldo Moro, and a Trainee Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) Therapist. Her research focus is mainly on attachment theory, post-traumatic stress disorders (PTSD), and developmental psychopathology. She is the author of two articles on childhood maltreatment and trauma-focused interventions: “Riconoscere e curare il trauma psicologico al tempo del Covid-19 nei bambini maltrattati” (with M. G. Foschino Barbaro & M. Pellegrini, 2021, *Cognitivismo Clinico*, 18(2), 217-226), and “Sfidarsi per esistere: ragazzi intrappolati nella rete tra vecchie e nuove forme di violenza” (with M. L. Disabato & M. G. Foschino Barbaro, 2022, *Psicoterapeuti in Formazione*, 29, 100-116).

Germana Castoro (Email: germana.castoro@policlinico.ba.it) is a Clinical Psychologist Psychotherapist at the Policlinico Giovanni XXIII Hospital of Bari. Her research activities focus on developmental attachment disorders, addictions and post-traumatic stress disorders. Her publications include the articles “Enhancing maternal sensitivity and infant attachment security with video feedback: An exploratory study in Italy” (with R. Cassibba, E. Costantino & G. Sette, 2015, *Infant Mental Health Journal*, 36(1), 53-61), and “Attachment security and language development in an Italian sample: The role of premature birth and maternal language” (with A. Costantini, R. Cassibba & G. Coppola, 2011, *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 36(2), 85-92).

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